

Multi-Purpose COTS-based Edge AI Computing Platform for Selective Compression in Small Satellites

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Introduction

AAC Hyperion and NLR are working on an integrated on-board AI acceleration solution specifically designed for remote sensing satellite missions with selective compression in mind.

This AOPU (AI Onboarding Processing Unit) solution have the following features:

- Low power (<10W)
- High Performance (8 TOPS)
- 1/2U form-factor, <0.5kg
- Fully integrated solution

There has been increased interest in selective compression due to its ability to reduce bandwidth usage and on-board storage. AI-based algorithms are suitable candidates for the selection of areas of interest as they can be trained for a specific use case such as object detection. However, computational complexity and restricted power constraints limit their use. Custom hardware for AI applications is expensive to develop and difficult to reuse for future missions, thus necessitating a reusable hardware platform.

We propose an AI hardware platform made from COTS parts designed to enable power efficient AI inference. The hardware focuses on being reusable for different missions.

Architecture

Figure 1. High-level architecture of the AOPU

The core architecture of the AOPU's deep learning implementation consists of a data pipeline of:

Image pre-processing → AI processing or inferencing → Image post-processing

Each of these stages is fully reconfigurable and shown visually in Figure 1. The AI processing stage supports popular deep learning frameworks such as TensorFlow and ONNX, which makes it easy for the user to deploy custom models on the computing platform. The architecture also allows for the storage and downloading of unprocessed data if so desired.

Figure 2a & 2b. Example Input image (2a) with selection of interest (2b) highlighted.

Figure 3a & 3b. 3a shows the radiation setup and 3b illustrates the diagram of the setup

Selective Compression Use-Case

To evaluate the AOPU's usefulness in selective compression, the performance of a ship detection algorithm was used.

The input images are a size of 1000x1000 pixels (split from a source image of 7150x5750 pixels) with a pixel depth of 12 bits. These are further pre-processed up to Level-1C for the AI inference stage. This selective compression AI neural network model is:

- Based on YOLOv5s architecture
- CNN (Convolutional Neural Network)
- ONNX runtime
- Trained on a Sentinel-2 image dataset

Radiation Robustness

Due to the harsh radiation environment during satellite missions, the electronics of the system must be robust to radiation. The Cobalt 60 radiation test setup can be seen in Figure 3a and a diagram of the setup can be seen in Figure 3b. The computing platform was exposed to a maximum dose of **51500 rad** over 6 days and the dosage was increased **379.3 rad per hour**.

A test suite was running on the module to test different peripherals, while test equipment was monitoring the different voltage supplies of the board.

No operational defects were found during this radiation test

Results

Table 1. The AOPU's performance in a set of sample neural networks

Network	Model Type	Input Image Size	FPS
ONR-CL-6060-mobileNetV1	Object Detection	224x224 pixels	635.06
ONR-CL-6072-mobileNetV2-1024x1024	Object Detection	1024x1024 pixels	92.63
ONR-CL-6142-regNetX-1.6gf-1024x1024	Image Classification	1024x1024 pixels	34.76

To further demonstrate the capabilities of the system, the AOPU was also tested with different neural network models common to on-board space-based applications. These tests are focused on the **Frames Per Second (FPS)** when computing large neural network models to show the potential of the AOPU module. The results of these tests are displayed in Table 1.

Next Steps

Future plans include:

- Further tuning of the selective image compression algorithm
- **Proton testing** of the hardware
- Continued development of the board and its software
- The use of **tiling multiple boards** for increased compute power

The final intent of this project is to offer a product that can fill the needs of any small or nano satellite mission which requires AI acceleration for selective compression or otherwise.

Find out more on:

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